

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF LASER THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC FOOT SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the research: in patients with diabetic foot syndrome, the use of intravenous laser irradiation and ultraviolet irradiation of blood contributes to the rapid cleaning of the wound surface from detritus, the acceleration of the formation and maturation of granulation tissue and wound epithelization is noted.

Keywords: diabetes, diabetic foot, intravascular laser irradiation of blood, ultraviolet irradiation of blood.

INTRODUCTION.

According to international statistics, as of now, about 200 million people in the world suffer from diabetes. In proportion to the increase in the incidence of diabetes, the number of its chronic complications also increases. The great social significance of complications of diabetes is that they lead to early disability and mortality, which is associated, in particular, with the development of diabetic foot syndrome. Despite the progress achieved in the study of the diabetic foot syndrome, the available data on the statistics of amputations are not optimistic. The reason is that 50-70% of all lower limb amputations are performed in patients with diabetes. The effectiveness of conservative treatment of diabetic patients with diabetic foot syndrome does not exceed 30%. To solve this problem, the use of physiotherapeutic methods of treatment, including plasma streams, high-energy and low-energy lasers, is proposed. In recent years, a number of works have proven the effectiveness of intravenous laser irradiation of blood (IVL) in the treatment of purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome. The wavelength of laser radiation of 635 nm (red spectrum) is optimal for the effect of improving the trophic supply of tissues through the following main mechanisms: increasing the deformation of erythrocyte membranes, increasing the level of erythrocyte content, improving the oxygen transport function of erythrocytes, improving blood rheology, etc. The wavelength of 405 nm combines the advantages of low-intensity laser radiation of the red and UV spectra, since for this wavelength the absorption maxima for both erythrocytes and immunocompetent cells coincide. [1,2]

There are many unsolved and controversial issues in the treatment of diabetic foot syndrome. The search for new effective means and methods of influencing the links of the pathogenesis of the diabetic foot syndrome continues. The introduction of new physical factors of influence, in particular intravenous laser irradiation of blood and ultraviolet irradiation of blood, opens up great possibilities for improving the results of treatment

of this category of patients. Ultraviolet irradiation of blood is one of the methods of quantum blood therapy, which has been widely used by domestic and foreign medicine for the past 20 years. The basis of the method is the irradiation of a small amount of blood flowing over a low-power ultraviolet light emitter, equal in intensity to sunlight in the ultraviolet spectrum. As a result of such influence, a certain group of molecules, highly sensitive to this spectrum of light, is excited. With the help of complex biochemical reactions, a general reaction of the whole organism develops, which includes a number of therapeutic effects that often exceed pharmacological therapy. The most important of them is the immunostimulating effect. Modern medicine does not know a more effective method of activating the body's immunity. Certain scientific articles have shown some positive aspects of the use of intravenous laser irradiation of blood at 405 nm and ultraviolet irradiation of blood in the treatment of diabetic patients with wounds that do not heal for a long time and trophic foot ulcers. However, the information and conclusions about the benefits of their use are insufficiently covered. There is no unity of opinion about the influence of these techniques on the course of the reparative process, regional microcirculation. The question of the expediency of their use depending on the form of the diabetic foot syndrome and the localization of the wound process is not reflected. The importance of the above problem for practical health care and the presence of many unexplored questions listed above served as the basis for this study. [2,3]

The aim of the study:

To develop a method of treatment of patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome using intravenous laser irradiation of blood (405 nm) and ultraviolet irradiation of blood and to give a comparative assessment of their effectiveness. [4]

Objectives of the study:

1. To develop and implement in clinical practice a method of treating patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome using intravenous laser

irradiation of blood (405 nm) and ultraviolet irradiation of blood.

2. To study the dynamics of the wound process during the treatment of patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome.

3. To provide a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of intravenous laser irradiation of blood (405 nm) and ultraviolet irradiation of blood in the treatment of patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome.

Research material:

An analysis of the results of the examination and treatment of 13 patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome who were treated in the surgical department of the regional hospital for the period from 2015 to 2019 was carried out. [7,8]

There were 8 (61.5%) women and 5 (38.4%) men among the patients. The age of the patients was from 45 to 64 years. All patients had type II diabetes. 9 (69.2%) patients were diagnosed with mild diabetes (fasting blood sugar in these patients was 8.2 mmol/l, 20-25 g in urine per day). 3 (23.07%) patients had diabetes of moderate severity. The glucose content in the fasting blood of these patients did not exceed 14 mmol/l, in the urine per day - no more than 40 grams, periodically acetone was detected in the urine. According to ultrasound, main blood flow at all levels of the affected limb was preserved in 10 (76.9%) patients, in 3 (23.07%) there were lesions of the arteries of the tibiofemoral segment. Despite various variants of stenoses of the arteries of the ankle-foot segment in the examined patients, there are no data on the presence of critical ischemia. [7,8]

Patients with diabetic foot syndrome were divided according to the depth of spread of the purulent-necrotic process: 1st group – 10 (76.9%), 2nd group – 3 (23.07%). According to the form of the diabetic foot: there were 9 (69.2%) patients with the neuropathic form of the diabetic foot, 4 patients (30.7%) with the neuroischemic form of the diabetic foot. [7,8]

The nature of purulent-necrotic lesions of the feet was represented by the following nosological forms: patients with dry gangrene of the foot comprised 3 (23.07%) patients, trophic ulcers – 2 (15.3%), purulent-necrotic foot wounds – 3 (23.07%), foot phlegmons – 5 (38.4%). When treating patients with diabetic foot syndrome, serious attention should be paid to the correction of concomitant diseases that complicate the course of the main disease. Ischemic heart disease was detected in 7 (53.8%) patients, hypertensive disease - in 4 (30.7%) patients, obesity of 2-3 degree - in 2 (15.3%) people, post-infarction cardiosclerosis - in 2 (15.3%) of patients. Treatment of concomitant diseases was carried out jointly with specialized specialists. [7,8]

The patients in the groups were comparable in terms of age, sex, localization and prevalence of the purulent process, presence of concomitant diseases. Treatment of patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome was comprehensive, including the impact on all pathogenetic links of the disease.

The scheme of treatment of patients included:

- surgical treatment;

- therapy aimed at compensating carbohydrate metabolism, according to the endocrinologist's recommendations (diet, tablet sugar-lowering drugs or insulin);

- antibacterial therapy (broad-spectrum antibiotics);

- detoxification therapy (in severe cases);

- metabolic therapy (alpha-lipoic acid, vitamins of group B);

- antiplatelet therapy (trental, sulodexide);

- local treatment included dressings with antiseptic solutions (Iodopyrine 1%, Chlorhexadine 0.1%), with enzymatic coatings (Dalcex-trypsin), hydrophilic ointments (Livosin, Levomekol), preparations based on hyaluronic acid (Kuriozin). [9,10]

Depending on the applied treatment methods, the patients were divided into 2 groups.

Group 1 (control) was represented by 6 (46.1%) patients who underwent traditional conservative therapy.

Group 2 (main) included 7 (53.8%) patients who, in addition to traditional therapy, underwent VLOK and UFO of blood. The power of laser radiation at the end of the light guide is 1.0 mW, the duration of action was 20 minutes per session. The course of laser therapy included 10 sessions. UVI of blood - the duration of action was 5-7 minutes per session. The course of therapy included 10 sessions. [9,10]

Research results and their discussion:

In patients of 1 (control) group, who received only traditional conservative treatment for up to 14 days, insignificant dynamics in changes in the clinical picture were noted. By this time of treatment, the swelling of the foot decreased in only 4 (67%) patients, and the pain syndrome was bought in only 2 (33%). In the 2nd (main) group, where, in addition to traditional therapy, IVLA and UVI of blood were performed, unlike the control group of patients, a decrease in foot pain and paraesthesia phenomena was noted for 7-10 days, a decrease in local edema was noted already on 4-5 days, hyperemia surrounding tissues for 2-3 days, and infiltration in the area of wound edges for 3-4 days.

The analysis of the main indicators of the course of the wound process in patients with diabetic foot syndrome in groups showed that in the group of patients treated with the traditional method, the average time for wound healing was 10±4 days, the appearance of granulation tissue was noted for 18±6 days, and healing (epithelialization for 50%) for 27±1 days. We noted the best indicators in group 2, where traditional conservative therapy and (IVLA)+UVI of blood were performed. The average time for cleaning wounds from damaged tissues was 5±2 days, the appearance of granulation tissue was noted for 14±2 days, and healing (50% epithelialization) for 21±1 days. [10]

Application of the developed method of treatment of wounds that do not heal for a long time and trophic ulcers in patients with purulent-necrotic forms of the diabetic foot syndrome contributed to a reduction in the time of cleaning wound defects by 1.5 times, the appearance of granulations by 1.4 times, and healing (epithelialization by 50%) in 1.3 times. In purulent-necrotic forms of the diabetic foot syndrome, depending

on the depth and area of the lesion, tissues remained non-viable in the wounds after surgical treatment, and secondary necrosis appeared in a number of cases during treatment, which required repeated surgical treatments. In the first group of 6 operated patients, repeated surgical treatment (necrectomy) was required for 4 (66.7%) patients. In the second group, where complex treatment with IVLA+UVI of blood was carried out, 1 (14.2%) of 7 patients also underwent repeated surgical treatment. As a rule, repeated surgical treatment was carried out 2-4 days after the primary one. The use of IVLA+UVI of blood made it possible to increase the effectiveness of postoperative treatment of wounds and reduce the number of repeated surgical treatments. IVLA+UVI of blood allows to shorten treatment and healing times in comparison with traditional methods, they are: the average time of inpatient treatment was 15 ± 1.5 days. In the comparison group (traditional treatment), these terms were significantly different and corresponded to 21.5 ± 1 days. [11]

The results of treatment were evaluated after 6 months. Clinical dynamics in patients with diabetic foot syndrome 6 months after treatment in the 2nd group, where IVLA+UVI blood was used, was characterized by an improvement in general well-being, a decrease in the feeling of "fatigue" in the legs, and a decrease in foot swelling. In the first group, the clinical picture corresponded to the same as before the start of the treatment course. [11,12]

We believe that the results of wound healing in patients with diabetic foot syndrome in group 2 are indicative. Among patients who received only traditional therapy, wound healing after 6 months was noted in 2 (33.4%) patients. Complex treatment of patients with diabetic foot syndrome, where traditional therapy was combined with IVLA+UVI blood, made it possible to achieve wound healing in 5 (71.5%) patients. [13,14]

Conclusions:

1. Using the method of complex treatment of purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome, based on the use of intravenous laser irradiation (405 nm) and ultraviolet irradiation of blood, according to clinical and laboratory studies, its therapeutic effectiveness can significantly exceed the effect of traditional therapy.

2. Clinical and laboratory studies in patients with purulent-necrotic forms of diabetic foot syndrome have shown that complex treatment using intravenous laser irradiation (405 nm) and ultraviolet irradiation of blood contribute to the rapid cleansing of the wound surface from purulent-necrotic detritus, the acceleration of formation and maturation is noted granulation tissue and epithelization of the wound by 1.3 times compared to the traditional method.

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